

Inter-Satellite Link Prediction with Supervised Learning: An Application in Sun-synchronous Orbits

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In the space industry, Distributed Space Systems are gaining importance for improving mission performance through collaboration and resource sharing among multiple satellites. When this collaboration requires communication between heterogeneous satellites, achieving satellite-autonomous cooperation is crucial to avoid complex centralized computations, ground dependencies, and extensive coordination efforts between stakeholders. Considering nano-satellites with limited resources, autonomy involves a cost-efficient method for predicting contact opportunities or Inter-satellite links (ISLs) to reduce energy wastage from unsuccessful communication attempts.

In this sense, our approach relies on a pre-trained Supervised Learning model to anticipate ISL opportunities between different pairs of Sun-synchronous orbit satellites. The contact opportunities are modeled as "close approach" considering the perturbations caused by Earth's shape and atmospheric drag. Results show that the SL model can anticipate two days of encounters with a Balanced Accuracy higher than 90% when compared with realistic data from an available database.

1 Introduction

The definition of sixth-generation wireless networks (6G) underscores a strong interest in Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs) [1]. With the increasing deployment of satellites and constellations into space, NTNs have emerged as a fundamental concept shaping the future of global connectivity, especially in remote areas. In response to this trend, Distributed Space Systems (DSS) are gaining significant importance [2]. Unlike conventional monolithic systems, DSS encompasses multiple satellites that collaborate to enhance overall mission performance across various domains including telecommunications, navigation, and Earth Observation.

Facilitating collaboration among heterogeneous satellites in a centralized manner demands extensive computation and coordination among various stake-

holders, a process that becomes increasingly unmanageable as more parties become involved. Moreover, centralized data processing lacks scalability and becomes unmanageable for mega-constellations. In response to these challenges, the space industry is moving towards a self-management system [3–6], where satellites can autonomously collaborate and share resources in real-time through Inter-Satellite Links (ISLs) to meet strict mission requirements and Quality of Service (QoS) without the need for ground segments and centralized computations.

Due to the limited resources on-board satellites, a crucial aspect of satellite-autonomous systems is enabling optimal and cost-efficient satellite communication. Due to satellite dynamics, ISL opportunities are intermittent, only available when satellites are within close range for effective information exchange. In that sense, cost-efficient satellite cooperation relies on anticipating the ISL opportunities to prevent energy wastage on false communication attempts and to allow the computation of optimal communication routes.

The satellite encounter anticipation problem has traditionally been solved based on deterministic orbital models [7]. While these solutions offer precise encounter forecasting, they can entail too high computational costs for limited resources systems such as nano-satellites. To avoid orbital propagation while maintaining a decentralized and autonomous approach, researchers in [8] have devised predictive algorithms for self-learning and constructing contact plans. Nevertheless, to mathematically formalize the solution, certain linearizations are applied, rendering them suitable only for concrete scenarios where satellites operate at the same altitude and follow perfect circular and Keplerian orbits.

Recent studies have explored the fusion of Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) with Recurrent Neural

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Networks (RNNs) to model the temporal evolution of dynamic systems [9–15]. Building on this trend, the feasibility of treating a constellation as a time-evolving graph and forecasting future node links based on historical data was investigated in [16], but dismissed due to its strong reliance on the past data. However, new studies [17] are further investigating the use of GNN-RNN to model constellations and provide optimal contact plans in heterogeneous systems in a cost-efficient and autonomous manner.

Based on previous publications [18], [19] using unrealistic data from circular, polar, and Kepler orbits, the present work showcases some advances in the proof of concept of using Supervised Learning (SL) to anticipate the communication opportunities between heterogeneous satellites assuming Simplified General Perturbation 4 (SGP4) orbit model. In particular, the encounter anticipation problem is solved for a specific type of Low-Earth polar orbit: the Sun-synchronous orbit (SSOs). While Low-Earth and polar orbits offer global Earth coverage with close proximity to the surface, SSOs also maintain a consistent orientation relative to the Sun, ensuring that satellites consistently observe the Earth’s surface under similar lighting conditions. This makes SSOs uniquely advantageous and ideal for Earth observation, representing about 70% of all Low-Earth polar orbits.

This work contributes to the state-of-the-art by (1) presenting a potentially cost-efficient alternative to forecasting encounters between satellites based on a realistic orbital model, (2) implementing a method to easily generate a synthetic dataset of satellite encounters given a range of orbital elements, (3) providing a SL model that accurately anticipates the encounters given any pair of orbital elements in the range of SSO under three different realistic scenarios, and (4) evaluating the SL model with realistic data from an available database for three different scenarios.

The remaining part of the article is organized as follows. In Section 2, the problem and the proposed solution based on machine learning are defined, outlining the structure of the datasets utilized for training, validation, and testing. The characteristics of SSOs used for synthetic data generation are presented in section 3. Section 4 provides a detailed explanation of the SL model architecture employed for processing the training input and output data. Section 5 evaluates the performance of the SL model by comparing its results with ground-truth synthetic and realistic test data. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper with a recap of

the main discoveries and offers insights for further exploration within this field.

2 Problem Statement

The communication opportunities between two satellites depend on their separation distance and the capabilities of their antennas. In this work, the communication opportunities are modeled as "close approaches", assuming that the satellites’ directional antennas are equipped with rapid pointing mechanisms, meaning an encounter (E) is detected when the distance between the satellites (D) is below a specified threshold (T), regardless of the pointing direction (see Figure 1). For modeling satellite trajectories, we adopt the well-known Simplified General Perturbations 4 (SGP4) model, which accounts for Earth’s shape and atmospheric drag perturbations.

Figure 1: Separation distance between two target satellites (in blue), threshold distance (dashed red line), and resulting binary encounter (in red). Time is discretized into intervals of 5 minutes, resulting in 576 binary values for 48 hours of encounters.

The proposed solution anticipates the next two days of encounters based on a SL model trained on-ground with an extensive collection of input-output samples. On one side, the input data comprises a set of samples containing the Orbital Elements (OEs) of different satellite pairs, a set of six values that describe the satellite’s position and orbit characteristics. To avoid issues arising from insufficient training data, this input dataset is generated synthetically following the OE characteristics of Sun-synchronous satellites explained in Section 3. On the other side, the output data defines 48 hours of encounters for each satellite pair in the input set, depicted by 576 binary features with a time discretization of 5 minutes. This output data is obtained by propagating each OE using SGP4, calculating the separation distance between satellite pairs (D), and then applying a distance threshold (T). Three different scenarios coming from three output datasets with different T s are used and compared in

Section 5.

A total of 1000 synthetic satellites are created for both training and validation: 813 for training and 187 for validation. This led to 660,969 (95%) training satellite pairs or samples and 34,969 (5%) validation samples. Additionally, a realistic set containing information on 200 SSO satellites from Celestrak [20] is used for testing in Section 5.

3 Sun-Synchronous Orbits

SSOs are a specific type of polar orbit for which the satellite’s orbital plane maintains a consistent orientation relative to the Sun, ensuring that satellites consistently observe the Earth’s surface under similar lighting conditions. SSOs exist only thanks to the effect of Earth’s oblateness, quantified by the second zonal term coefficient (J_2). J_2 gradually modifies the Right Ascension of the Ascending Node angle (Ω), producing a precession rate (ρ) defined in Equation 1 [21]. Notice that, the orbital elements a , i , and e must be carefully designed to follow the motion of the Earth about the Sun with a precession rate of 360 degrees per sidereal year. However, in a real scenario, SSOs can be defined with a range of ρ s close to this theoretical value. In this sense, it is assumed that all satellites with a precession rate 20% lower or higher than 1 degree per day are sun-synchronized.

$$\rho = \dot{\Omega}t = -\frac{3J_2R_E^2\sqrt{\mu}\cos i}{2a^{7/2}(1-e^2)^2} \quad (1)$$

where R_E and μ are two Earth constants standing for the mean radius and the standard gravitational parameter, respectively.

Figure 2: Precession rate for a total of 6930 satellites. Positive precession rates are associated with inclinations higher than 90°, while negative precessions (opposed to the Earth’s revolution) are associated with inclinations lower than 90°.

Figure 2 illustrates the precession rate for a total of 6930 real and active satellites obtained from Celestrak (the total number of satellites available in the database at the beginning of 2023). The dashed red line indicates the ρ value that makes the orbit Sun-synchronized, notated as ρ_{SS} . Considering that the mean motion of the Earth about the Sun is 360 degrees per sidereal year, the theoretical ρ_{SS} value is 0.98561 °/day. However, in a real scenario, SSOs are defined with a range of ρ s close to the theoretical value ρ_{SS} . In this work, it is assumed that all satellites with a precession rate within 20 % of ρ_{SS} are sun-synchronous. This region of interest, ranging from 0.8 ° per day to 1.2 ° per day, includes 1,834 satellites, which is approximately 25% of the total satellites listed in the Celestrak database at the beginning of 2023.

Additionally, to accurately replicate real SSOs with synthetic data, a detailed analysis of the six orbital elements for all 1834 SSO satellites is conducted. Table 1 summarizes the findings with the OE value ranges. Due to the Earth observation mission purpose, SSOs are quasi-circular and within the Low-Earth orbit (LEO) altitude range. Additionally, since Ω , ω , and M_0 are not present in the definition of SSOs, the whole range of values is present. Notice that the inclination of each synthetic SSO satellite should be subsequently inferred from a , e , and ρ by following the definition in equation 1.

Finally, the synthetic dataset to train the model, containing a set of initial state or OEs, is obtained by combining random values for a , e , Ω , ω , M , and ρ within their respective specified ranges.

a	e	i	Ω	ω	M	ρ
[km]	[-]	[°]	[°]	[°]	[°]	[°/day]
[6700, 7500]	[0, 0.02]	-	[0, 360]	[0, 360]	[0, 360]	[0.8, 1.2]

Table 1: OE ranges for Sun-Synchronous Orbits.

4 Supervised Learning Architecture

As explained in Section 1, the proposed solution to anticipate the communication opportunities between two given satellites is based on the well-known Supervised Learning (SL) technique. Unlike other machine learning solutions, SL learns from labeled

data, meaning that, given a sufficient number of labeled inputs and training epochs, the model can learn the relationship between the input and the output labels. In that sense, taking advantage of the cost-efficient model inference, our goal is to directly obtain the encounters using a pre-trained model, eliminating the need for orbital propagation and the subsequent satellite-to-satellite distance calculations and threshold distance evaluations.

The architecture of the Fully-Connected Neural Network (FCNN) has been reused from [18], with 6 fully connected hidden layers, each containing 32, 64, 128, 128, 256, and 256 neurons. Additionally, the input and the output layers contain 12 and 576 neurons to accommodate both OE pairs of synthetic SSO satellites and 2 days of binary encounters, respectively. It is important to note that increasing the number of hidden layers and neurons per layer increases the computational time needed to infer the solution. In that sense, the present work aims to showcase that SL can achieve high-accuracy predictions of encounters without relying on orbital propagation, leaving resource optimization tasks for future work.

5 Results

In this section, the performance of the SL model architecture is evaluated across three distinct scenarios corresponding to three different distance thresholds based on [22]: $T = 1,500$ km, $T = 2,000$ km, and $T = 2,500$ km. It is important to note that each threshold results in slightly different encounters and thus, each one requires specific training with the same input but distinct output data.

Figure 3(a) provides a comparison between the model predictions (in green) and the ground truth encounters (in red) for FLOCK 4X-40 and LEDSAT on January 4th, 2023, using three different thresholds T s. Notice that the lower the threshold, the shorter the contact times (or the number of ones) present in the output data. Considering that binary encounter sequences are usually in low values, using the Accuracy to evaluate the performance is not a good approach. Instead, a common practice when dealing with unbalanced datasets is to use the Balanced Accuracy (BA), which averages the Accuracy in predicting low values and high values (see Equation 2).

$$BA = \frac{TPR + TNR}{2} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{TP}{TP + FN} + \frac{TN}{TN + FP} \right) \quad (2)$$

where TPR , TNR , TP , TN , FP , and FN stand for True Positive Rate (also called Recall), True Negative Rate, True Positive, False Positive, and False Negative, respectively.

Note that TPR below 1 indicates that some communication opportunities are not detected, while TNR lower than 1 means that some energy could be lost if a transmission takes place during a false encounter. To compute these binary metrics and evaluate BA , the model prediction must be post-processed to a binary signal using a decision threshold (black dashed line in Figure 3(a)). Adjusting the threshold can influence the trade-off between maximizing the number of correctly detected encounters (by reducing the threshold) and minimizing false encounters (by increasing it). Assuming a default decision threshold of 0.5, Figure 3(b) shows the distribution of BA for each scenario with different T s considering all satellites in the Celestrak test dataset. These results show that the distribution of BA is very similar for all scenarios and does not depend on T s. Although the minimum threshold presents the highest pick of maximum BA , the mean BA is around 93% for all three cases.

To clarify the previous discussion regarding the impact of the decision threshold, Figure 3(c) shows the Precision-Recall curve (PRC). Similar to TNR , Precision (P) indicates the proportion of wasted energy by computing the probability of estimating a contact inside the true time slot. As expected from previous results, the area under the PRC, also called Average Precision (AP), remains stable at approximately 97%.

T	1500 km	2000 km	2500 km
BA [%]	93.2	93.3	93.3
Precision [%]	92.1	92.3	92.6
Recall [%]	86.9	87.1	87.5
F1 score [%]	87.0	87.1	88.5
AP [%]	96.8	97.0	97.1

Table 2: Mean performance obtained with Celestrak dataset for each distance threshold T .

To summarize, Table 2 presents the mean values for all metrics, including the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall, known as the F1 score. Notice that Precision is always higher than Recall, indicating the model prioritizes minimizing false encounters or energy wasted, rather than maximizing the predicted

Figure 3: SL model performance with Celestrak test set with different distance thresholds (T_s). (a) True encounters and model prediction between FLOCK 4X-40 (Norad ID: 51052) and LEDSAT (Norad ID: 49069) on January 4th, 2023. (b) Balanced Accuracy probability distribution for all satellite pairs in test datasets. (c) Precision-Recall curve.

communication opportunities. This behavior comes from the reduced number of true communication opportunities in the ground truth (dataset unbalance), causing the model to tend to predict lower values rather than higher ones. If more encounters are to be detected, the decision threshold should be decreased.

6 Discussion

This work demonstrates that a SL approach based on synthetic data can anticipate the encounters between realistic SSO satellites from Celestrak. The synthetic input consists of a 12-dimension vector containing the initial state of different satellite pairs. The training process tries to map the input data into a 576-dimension binary sequence describing the next 48 hours of encounters. Encounters are defined to occur when the satellite-to-satellite distance falls below a specified threshold T . Three different T_s have been used to evaluate the model performance: 1,500 km, 2,000 km, and 2,500 km.

Results indicate that despite training with synthetic and uniformly distributed data across the whole LEO SSO space, the model can infer the encounters for realistic data from Celestrak satellites, non-uniformly distributed across different constellations. Strong performance is observed with a Balanced Accuracy and Average Precision of around 93% and 97%, respectively.

Future work will include modeling the entire Polar LEO space and comparing the computational time of SL model inference with that of orbit propagation.

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